

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION THROUGH PROJECT-BASED ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *This article provides a scholarly and theoretical analysis of the concept of contemporary education, its substantive characteristics and the role of subject–object relationships within the education system. Within the framework of the core educational concept, the study examines the qualities that are considered priorities in the operation of the higher education system. The goals and objectives of the educational process, the methods of its implementation, and the outcomes to be achieved are discussed in an interconnected manner. Based on an analysis of scientific literature and empirical studies, the principal mental models underlying students' choice of higher education are identified. In close connection with these models, the pedagogical significance of the “project-based activity” approach in higher education and its role in enhancing educational effectiveness are substantiated.*

Keywords: *higher education, specialization, subject–object relationships, intellectual development, educator, educational process, transactional model, research model, competence, project-based activity.*

Introduction

Owing to rapid advances in science and technology worldwide, new sectors of production are emerging, and the demand for specialists equipped with modern knowledge and skills is steadily increasing. This situation makes the task of training human resources that meet labour-market requirements a pressing priority for higher and secondary specialized education systems. At the same time, a decline—or even the complete disappearance—of demand for certain traditional specializations necessitates a revision of educational content and structure. In response to these developments, comprehensive reforms aimed at modernizing education systems are being implemented in developed countries, accompanied by an ongoing transformation of educational processes. Taking international experience into account, additional measures have also been adopted in our country to accelerate educational reforms, further deepen ongoing changes in the sector, organize the activities of educational institutions on the basis of advanced international practices, and improve the system of teacher training.

In recent years, normative legal documents adopted in the Republic in the field of education have stipulated a reduction in the number of specializations at the bachelor's and master's levels by 40% and 15%, respectively. This, in turn, requires the preparation not of narrowly specialized personnel, but rather of universal specialists possessing foundational knowledge and competencies across multiple fields. Let us consider an analysis of existing challenges in higher education. To effectively accomplish these important tasks facing the higher education system, it is necessary to introduce relevant modifications to the current higher education concept. First and foremost, this requires a comprehensive examination of the problems currently observed in higher education, the factors underlying their emergence, and the social demand of society and the labour market. On

the basis of such an analysis, it becomes possible to clearly define strategic goals and key objectives of education.

It is well known that any educational process is grounded in interactions between a subject and an object, and it is precisely through this interaction that educational activity is formed. In contemporary pedagogical theories, qualitative changes in education have been achieved by revisiting subject–object relations and elevating them to the level of subject–subject relations. In the national education system as well, there is a need for an in-depth analysis of the traditional model of education in order to improve educational effectiveness and develop it in line with modern requirements. In this regard, it is essential first to focus on the meaning and essence of the concepts of “education” and “educational process,” as well as their structural characteristics.

Education is aimed at ensuring an individual’s intellectual, spiritual, moral, creative, physical, and professional development, and it encompasses a set of knowledge, skills, abilities, experience, and competencies of sufficient scope and complexity to satisfy the individual’s interests and needs. Since the educational process is typically implemented as an activity directed by the teacher toward the learner or student, the notions of “educational process” and “pedagogical process” are close in meaning. The traditional educational process, as the dominant form of pedagogical activity, presupposes organizing purposeful influence on the learner or student in order to shape a личности (personality) that corresponds to society’s social demand.

In contemporary education, however, the primary emphasis shifts from teacher-directed influence toward the student to their mutual interaction, supplemented by the students’ independent activity. Therefore, the learner or student is regarded as a full-fledged subject who must understand the educational goal, accept its relevance for oneself, and possess motivation. When the educational process is organized on the basis of this principle, the student encounters questions, tasks, and problems and, in solving them, draws upon existing and newly acquired knowledge and skills, analyses the solution, derives conclusions, and generates further new knowledge. The above constitutes the core concept of education; however, its implementation also requires attention to educational content, teacher–student activity within the educational process, and the outcomes to be achieved. The goal, objectives, implementation methods, and results are considered the main structural components of the educational process. According to the literature review, it can be understood that the educational process essentially consists of four core components, namely:

- educational goals;
- educational content;
- instructional/learning activities;
- learning outcomes.

Secondary and higher education systems have both shared and distinctive goals, which are determined by the objectives and expected outcomes of each educational level. Taking these aspects into account, Howard Gardner and Wendy Fishman—professors at the Harvard Graduate School of Education—conducted research at a number of leading universities in the United States and Europe to clarify the goals of higher education and to identify criteria for evaluating high-quality higher education. The researchers concluded that, to achieve the aims of higher education effectively, institutional goals should be aligned with students’ personally set goals. Therefore, the study placed particular emphasis on first identifying students’ motivations and intended purposes for entering higher education.

Based on survey findings, students were classified into four major mental models according to their motivation for choosing higher education. The first group, the inertial mental model, included students who entered higher education after completing secondary school without clear, consciously formulated goals or professional plans, largely under the influence of general social momentum. The second group, the transactional mental model, comprised students who viewed higher education primarily as a means to obtain a diploma, expand social networks, and secure successful professional employment in the future. The third group was characterized by the research-oriented mental model. Students within this model entered higher education to realize their interests through engagement with various disciplines and fields of activity, as well as through scientific and intellectual interaction with instructors and peers. The fourth group, the transformational mental model, included students who perceived higher education as an opportunity for self-understanding, personal development, and the discovery of new knowledge and experiences.

Analysis of the survey results indicated that approximately 50% of students belonged to the transactional mental model, while about 5% were associated with the inertial model. The remaining ~45% of students fell into the research-oriented and transformational mental model groups. During the study, an analysis conducted among graduates—based on the question “What did you achieve during your higher education experience?”—introduced the concept of “higher education capital” into scholarly discourse. This concept was interpreted as an indicator reflecting the level of development of a student’s thinking activity—specifically, skills related to reasoning, analysis, and effective communication—and was assessed using a three-point scale.

The results demonstrated a direct relationship between the type of mental model and higher education capital. In particular, among students who received the highest scores, the proportion of those with a transformational mental model was relatively high, whereas the lowest scores were predominantly associated with representatives of the transactional mental model. According to the researchers, many higher education institutions have traditionally organized their activities largely around the transactional model. Although this approach produced positive outcomes in earlier periods, in recent years it has not ensured high levels of graduate success. This is because the model primarily emphasizes narrowly targeted preparation for professional activity. While such an approach may have been economically justified during a certain phase, under contemporary conditions it is gradually losing its effectiveness.

Discussion

Distinctive features of “project-based activity” in higher education. Findings from contemporary pedagogical research indicate that priority should be given to approaches in the educational process that foster the development of cognitive activity, cultivate independent thinking, and support students’ creative and innovative potential. Such approaches are largely consistent with the research-oriented and transformational mental models. In this regard, researchers emphasize that higher education institutions, based on the specific characteristics of their mission and context, should formulate clear strategic objectives and systematically internalize these objectives among both faculty members and students. Empirical evidence suggests that when the educational process in higher education institutions is organized around research-oriented and transformational mental models, educational effectiveness increases substantially. An illustrative example is UNIST (Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology), established in the Republic of Korea in 2007. As of 2024, UNIST ranked 212th in the QS World University Rankings and 8th nationally within South Korea; this achievement is often attributed, among other factors,

to the extensive implementation of research-oriented and transformational approaches in teaching and learning.

Accordingly, based on these recommendations, each higher education institution should define its goals in consideration of its capacities, internal resources, and the social demand of society, and develop mechanisms for achieving these goals. This, first and foremost, requires the scientifically grounded design of educational content and the purposeful organization of the activities of both faculty and students. From this perspective, each institution should revisit the substantive components of its curriculum, clearly determine which components should receive priority attention, and specify what new elements should be incorporated into the educational content. While the traditional education model primarily aims to develop predefined knowledge, skills, and abilities in students, the learner-centred model, in addition to these elements, also encompasses the enrichment of personal experience through interaction with the educational environment.

Moreover, the competency-based approach is widely applied in modern education systems. Within this framework, special emphasis is placed on students' acquisition of universal (transferable) competencies, regardless of the specific profession or specialization for which they are being trained. The central component of the educational process is recognized as activity based on interaction between the teacher and the student. The structure of instructional activity comprises various forms and methods. Depending on the quantitative configuration of teacher–student interactions, instructional formats may be organized as individual, small-group, collective, or whole-class (frontal) modes.

Recommendations

Across all instructional formats, the quality of the knowledge delivered to students, the degree to which it is mastered, and the effectiveness of developing professional or general competencies depend directly on the teaching methods employed in the educational process. Given that the goal-oriented, systematic, and organized activity of the teacher and the student manifests itself as a teaching method, contemporary education requires the selection of pedagogical methods that can, as far as possible, encompass diverse forms of teaching and learning. Today, “project-based activity” is widely used in the practice of leading higher education institutions and general education schools worldwide as one of the effective pedagogical methods. This approach belongs to the category of active learning methods, in which the student is not a passive participant in the educational process but rather acts as an independent subject of learning. Project-based activity integrates various forms of cognitive, exploratory, analytical, planning, and practical actions on the part of the student and, for this reason, can be differentiated into several types.

Although scholarly sources emphasize the high effectiveness of applying the project-based activity method in higher education institutions, a fully developed universal model of this approach across all fields of study has not yet been established. In particular, within undergraduate physics curricula, approaches aimed at the systematic and comprehensive integration of project-based activity have not been sufficiently developed. A newly admitted university student may structure the process of achieving their educational goals—over the period from the first to the fourth year—into several consecutive stages of project-based activity. At the initial stage, an undergraduate physics student, after becoming familiar with the curriculum and course syllabi, should plan and develop, for example, three or four projects focused on mastering the “Mechanics” module in order to earn the required credits. In doing so, the student is expected to: determine the level of mastery of the topics in the syllabus; identify scientific and physical concepts that are new and challenging;

and analyze the extent to which these concepts and topics are interconnected with previously acquired knowledge.

At this stage, students are typically not prepared to carry out these activities fully independently. Therefore, in the case of first-year undergraduate physics students, intensive pedagogical support from faculty members and tutors of the Department of General Physics is required. In this process, the regular implementation of various assessment tasks, oral questioning, consultations, and monitoring activities is of particular importance. Based on conversations with faculty members and tutors, as well as the results of assessments, it is advisable to group students and define mastery of the mechanic's module as the central project task for each group. The coherent sequencing and consistent implementation of the planned activities should be subject to continuous monitoring. In subsequent stages, the primary objective is to transition toward students' independent planning of project-based activity and to ensure that they can autonomously design and implement educational-methodological, research, or applied projects on specific topics.

Conclusion

A number of scientific studies have been conducted internationally and within the education system of the Republic regarding the implementation of project-based activity across all levels of education. These studies have substantiated that the use of project-based activity in the educational process yields high pedagogical effectiveness. However, although the application of this approach in higher education institutions has produced positive results in certain fields, generalized and conclusive scientific findings across all educational domains have not yet been fully established. In particular, within undergraduate physics curricula, methodological support aimed at introducing project-based activity on a systematic and comprehensive basis remains insufficiently developed. As a result, the integration of project-based activity into the instructional process of this field continues to be largely fragmentary. At the same time, if students acquire the necessary skills and competencies to implement project-based activity effectively during higher education, graduates will subsequently be able to independently design and implement projects when mastering new scientific areas or professional fields. This, in turn, enhances graduates' professional adaptability, enabling them to transition from one field to another with fewer difficulties and supporting their continuous professional development.

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